

To Study the Expression and Prognostic Significance of Immunoregulatory Molecule Pd-L1 in Oral Squamous Cell Carcinoma and Pre-Cancerous Oral Epithelial Lesions

Mohd Daud Akhtar¹, Nishat Afroze², Veena Maheswari³, Murad Ahmed⁴, Kratee⁵

¹Junior Resident, Department of Pathology, JNMC, AMU, Aligarh, UP

²Professor, Department of Pathology, JNMC, AMU, Aligarh, UP

³Professor, Department of Pathology, JNMC, AMU, Aligarh, UP

⁴Assistant Professor, Department of Pathology, JNMC, AMU, Aligarh, UP

⁵Junior Resident, Department of Pathology, JNMC, AMU, Aligarh, UP

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Corresponding Author: Mohd Daud Akhtar

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Abstract:

Background: Oral cancer is the sixth most common malignancy worldwide, and it is characterized by high morbidity and mortality rates. Oral squamous cell carcinoma (OSCC) accounts for more than 90% of all oral malignancies.

Aims & Objectives: The present study was done to analyse the immune-expression of PD-L1 in OSCC and precancerous oral epithelial lesions. Also, the statistical association between PDL-1 expression and clinicopathological features with special reference to tumour size, histological grade, tumour depth, stromal lymphocyte reaction, nodal status and tumour stage was done to determine the significance of PD-L1 expression as a predictive and prognostic biomarker in OSCC.

Materials & Methods: It was a prospective study conducted on 232 cases (211 OSCC + 21 premalignant lesions) of which 86 cases (65 OSCC + 21 premalignant lesions) were selected, and results analyzed with clinical parameters. Immunohistochemistry (IHC) for Programmed death ligand 1 (PD-L1) molecules was applied.

Results: In our study a significant statistical correlation was found between the immuno-expression of PD-L1 in tumour cells and tumour grade, degree of stromal lymphocyte reaction, tumour size, cervical lymph node status and tumour stage. Higher tumour grade and higher TNM stage were significantly associated with higher expression of PD-L1

Conclusions: Significant correlation of PD-L1 with different clinico-pathological variables especially tumor grade and TNM stage can help in the prediction of the prognosis of these patients and can also help guide the response to the treatment given in higher stage tumour, specially with the promising PD-L1 monoclonal antibodies.

Keywords: PD-L1, Oral Squamous Cell Cancer (OSCC).

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Background

Oral cancer is the sixth most common malignancy worldwide, and it is characterized by high morbidity and mortality rate. [1] Oral squamous cell carcinoma (OSCC) accounts for more than 90% of oral malignancy. [2] Traditionally, it is identified as oral squamous cell carcinoma (OSCC) since, in the dental region, 90% of cancers originate histologically from squamous cells. [3] Different histological types of oral cancer includes squamous cell carcinoma (SCC), adenosquamous cell carcinoma, adenoid cystic carcinoma, osteosarcoma, and mucoepidermoid carcinoma. However among these SCC is the most common type. [4] Cancer development is also influenced by factors such as human papillomavirus infection,

genetic predisposition, oral hygiene, smoking, alcohol consumption, and the use of areca nuts. [5,6] Most cases of oral squamous cell carcinoma are derived from oral premalignant lesions or conditions, including oral submucous fibrosis (OSF). [7] In India, oral cancer constitutes a significant portion of the total cancer cases, accounting for approximately 30 to 40%. The primary cause of this disease is the excessive consumption of tobacco products, which can be either smoked or used as smokeless chewing products.

The incidence of oral cancer is particularly high in Uttar Pradesh and other regions of North India. This alarming trend can be attributed to the

widespread use of smokeless tobacco products such as paan and gutkha among the younger population. These products, despite their harmful effects, continue to be popular, contributing to the high prevalence of oral cancer in these areas. [8]

In most of the countries, the male population is more commonly involved and these sex differences are attributable to heavier indulgence in risk habits by men and exposure to sunlight (for lip cancer) as a part of outdoor occupations. [9] Potentially malignant disorders (PMDs) include inflammatory oral submucosal fibrosis, erythroplakia, leukoplakia, candidal leukoplakia and lichen planus. [10] The three main treatment modalities are surgery, radiation therapy and chemotherapy. Recent advancements in the field of reconstructive surgery have significantly improved the prognosis for patients diagnosed with OSCC. These innovative surgical techniques and procedures have not only enhanced the survival rates but also improved the quality of life for these patients. [11]

Programmed death ligand-1 (PD-L1) /Programmed death-1 (PD-1) axis plays a very important role in evasion of tumour cells from the immune system and immune checkpoint blockade have led to the development of therapies which are proven effective in melanoma and non-small cell lung cancer. [12] PD-L1 is also known as B7-H1 and CD274. It is a type I transmembrane glycoprotein expressed on antigen-presenting cells and some tumour cells, including melanoma, ovarian, and lung cancer cells. PD-L1 is a ligand for PD-1 and this binding results in inhibition of T-cell effector functions leading to the escape of tumour cells from immune response

Aims & Objectives

The study's objective was to investigate the immune-expression of PD-L1 in Oral Squamous Cell Carcinoma (OSCC) and precancerous oral epithelial lesions. It aimed to establish a statistical correlation between PD-L1 expression and various clinicopathological features such as tumor size, histological grade, tumor depth, stromal lymphocyte reaction, nodal status, and tumor stage. Additionally, the study explored the potential of PD-L1 expression as a predictive and prognostic biomarker in OSCC.

Materials & Methods

Research ethics: Ethical clearance was obtained from the Institutional Ethics Committee. Informed consent was taken from each patient or his attendant wherever patient was not in a condition to provide consent. Privacy and confidentiality of collected information was ensured throughout the process.

Sample selection: This prospective study involved total of 232 cases, comprising 211 instances of Oral

Squamous Cell Carcinoma (OSCC) and 21 premalignant lesions. These cases were examined for clinicopathological characteristics. Out of these, 86 cases (which included 65 OSCC and 21 premalignant lesions) were selected for Immunohistochemistry (IHC). The results obtained from the IHC were then correlated with the clinicopathological features. Patients were enrolled in the study based on specific inclusion and exclusion criteria. The inclusion criteria consisted of patients who had tissue biopsies of Oral Squamous Cell Carcinoma (OSCC). The exclusion criteria included patients with oral epithelial premalignant lesions, those who refused consent, those with non-neoplastic lesions or non-squamous cell malignancies, and patients who had previously received neoadjuvant chemotherapy and radiotherapy.

Immunohistochemistry (IHC): The histopathological tissues were preserved in a 10% formalin solution. Sections of the paraffin block, each measuring 4-5 μm in thickness, were cut and stained using Hematoxylin and Eosin. PD-L1 Immunohistochemical staining was applied on 3-4 μm thick sections as per the kit manufacturer's instructions. These OSCC samples were classified into well-differentiated, moderately differentiated and poorly differentiated types according to the World Health Organization (WHO) classification of tumours of the oral cavity and oropharynx. [El-Naggar et al., 2017] [13] The intensity of the stromal lymphocytic reaction in OSCC was categorized into three levels: slight or absent, moderate, and severe. [Kouketsu et al., 2019]. [14] The pathological diagnosis of Oral Epithelial Premalignant Lesion was classified according to the WHO classification of head and neck tumours as mild dysplasia, moderate dysplasia and severe dysplasia [El-Naggar et al., 2017]. [13] Tonsil and normal oral tissue was selected as positive and negative control respectively. [Lin et al., 2015]. [15] The region at the invasive edge of the tumor, which included both tumor cells and infiltrating stromal lymphocytes within and around the tumor, was chosen for examination. Selected cases were picked to study the immunohistochemical (IHC) expression of PD-L1 in the tumor cells. The assessment of PD-L1 immuno-expression was conducted based on the intensity and percentage of staining observed in the membrane and/or cytoplasm of the tumor cells, following the protocols established in earlier studies. [Kouketsu et al., 2019, Koh et al., 2015] [15,16]. Immunohistochemical reactivity for PD-L1 was graded as per Kouketsu et al., 2019. [14] i.e. Score 0 Negative, Score 1 Weakly positive (scatteredly positive in <25% of the epithelial/tumour cells), Score 2 Moderately positive (scatteredly positive in >25% of the epithelial/tumour cells). Score 3 Strongly positive (continuously positive in >25% of

the epithelial/tumour cells). The observations were statistically analyzed using the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) software (v.23, USA) and Microsoft Excel. The association between categorical variables was examined using Pearson's chi-square test. A p-value of less than 0.05 was considered significant.

Observations & Results

This prospective study was conducted on a total of 211 histopathologically diagnosed cases of oral squamous cell carcinomas (OSCC) and 21 squamous premalignant lesions received in the histopathology section over the period of 2 years. Out of 211 cases of Oral Squamous Cell Carcinoma (OSCC), 65 cases spanning all three grades of the tumor were selected. Immunohistochemistry (IHC) was then performed for PD-L1 on these selected cases. Twenty-nine cases of well differentiated OSCC, 19 cases of moderately differentiated OSCC and 17 cases of poorly differentiated OSCC were analyzed whereas 21 premalignant lesions were selected out of which 7 cases were of mild dysplasia, 9 of moderate dysplasia and 5 of severe dysplasia.

In our study the most common age group affected by OSCC was 40-49 years followed by 50-59 years. Out of 211 cases, 66(23.2%) cases were found in 40-49 age group and 52(11.8%) cases were present in the 50-59 age group. Out of 211 cases, 178(84.3%) were males and only 33(15.6%) were females with M:F ratio being 5:1. Out of total 211 OSCC, 107 (50.7%) cases were of well differentiated OSCC, 87(41.2%) cases were of moderately differentiated OSCC and 17(%) cases were of poorly differentiated OSCC. The majority of the cases were found on the tongue, accounting for 43.6% of the total. This was followed by cases on the buccal mucosa, which constituted 37.4% of the cases. The least number of cases were located on angle of mouth and floor of mouth which accounted for 0.9% each. Out of 65 cases of OSCC, PD-L1 immuno-expression was observed in 50.7% cases. Among the premalignant lesions 62% cases showed immuno-expression for PD-L1. The p-value of PD-L1 positive versus negative cases among OSCC and premalignant conditions was found to be 0.37. This is considered insignificant as the p-value is greater than 0.05. When comparing the grades, poorly differentiated OSCC cases showed the highest number of PD-L1 immuno-expression, accounting for 88.2% (15 out of 17 cases). In contrast, well-differentiated OSCC cases showed PD-L1 immuno-expression in only 27.5% of cases (8 out of 29 cases). The difference in PDL-1 positive versus negative staining score among different histopathological grades was statistically significant ($p=0.00036$). Of the total 65 cases, 32(49.2%) were completely negative for PD-L1 exhibiting score 0. However, of the remaining 33

positive cases (50.8 %); 8(12.3%) cases were weakly positive (score 1), 9(13.8%) cases were moderately positive (score 2) and 16(24.6%) cases were strongly positive (score 3) for PD-L1. When examined based on histopathological grades, only 1 case of well-differentiated OSCC exhibited a PD-L1 score of 3. In contrast, 12 out of 17 cases of poorly differentiated OSCC demonstrated a PD-L1 score of 3. This suggests a higher PD-L1 expression in poorly differentiated OSCC.

The p-value of PD-L1 was found to be statistically significant i.e., $p<0.001$. When comparing the intensity scores of immunoreactivities of PDL-1 among different histopathological grades it was found that maximum number of poorly differentiated OSCC (70.5%) showed higher intensity score compared to well differentiated OSCC(3.4%) and the difference was found to be statistically significant ($p<0.05$).

Out of the total 21 cases of squamous dysplasia, 62% exhibited immuno-expression for PD-L1 in dysplastic cells. Moreover, among the three types of histopathological dysplasia, moderate dysplasia had the highest number of cases showing PD-L1 immuno-expression, accounting for 66.6% (6 out of 9 cases). This suggests a significant presence of PD-L1 in moderate dysplasia. The observed difference in PDL-1 staining among different types of dysplasia was statistically insignificant ($p>0.05$). Out of the total 21 cases, 8 cases (38%) showed no immuno-expression for PD-L1 in dysplastic cells, exhibiting a score of 0. Of the remaining 13 cases, 7 cases (33.3%) were weakly positive (score 1), 5 cases (23.8%) were moderately positive (score 2), and 1 case (4.7%) was strongly positive (score 3) for PD-L1. Only one case of moderate dysplasia showed a PD-L1 score of 3, while the majority of the cases exhibited PD-L1 scores of 0 and 1. This suggests varying levels of PD-L1 expression across the cases. When comparing the intensity scores of immunoreactivities of PDL-1 in dysplastic cells among different types of dysplasia it was found that maximum number of cases with moderate dysplasia showed higher intensity score compared to mild dysplasia but the difference was found to be statistically insignificant ($p>0.05$).

According to degree of stromal lymphocyte reaction 61.6% (11/18) having absent/mild TILs showed PD-L1 score 3 whereas 75%(27/36) having marked TILs showed PD-L1 score 0. When comparing the intensity scores of immunoreactivities of PDL-1 among different degrees of stromal lymphocyte reaction it was observed that maximum number of OSCC with absent/mild TILs showed higher intensity score compared to presence of markedly denser TILs around tumour cells and the difference was found to be statistically significant ($p<0.05$).

Based on tumor size, T3 stage OSCC showed PD-L1 immuno-expression in majority of cases comprising of 84.6% (11/13) cases unlike T2 stage OSCC which showed PD-L1 immuno-expression in 52.3% (11/21) cases. The difference in PD-L1 staining among different TNM stage groups was statistically significant ($p < 0.05$). Out of 65 patients with OSCC, follow-up was possible for 36 patients over a period of one year. Of these, 7 cases (19.4%) showed tumor recurrence, while 29 cases (80.5%) showed no recurrence at the one-year follow-up. An assessment was conducted to examine the

relationship between tumor recurrence and the immuno-expression of PD-L1. This could provide valuable insights into the role of PD-L1 in tumor progression and recurrence. Out of the 7 cases that showed tumor recurrence, PD-L1 immuno-expression was observed in 71.4% (5 out of 7 cases). On the other hand, OSCC cases without tumor recurrence showed PD-L1 immuno-expression in 82.7% of cases. The p-value of PD-L1 was found to be 0.4966. This suggests that the association of positive PD-L1 with tumor recurrence was statistically insignificant ($p > 0.05$).

Figure 1A

Figure 1B

Figure 1C

Figure 1D

Figure 2A

Figure 2B

Figure 2C

Figure 2D

Figure 3A

Figure 3B

Figure 3C

Figure 3D

Discussion

In our study the most common age group affected by OSCC was 40-49 years followed by 50-59 years. Out of 211 cases in our study 66(23.2%) cases were found in 40-49 age group and 52(11.8%) cases were present in the 50-59 age group. According to Yoshida et al.,2018 the most common age group was 70-79 years (34.07%) followed by 60-69 years(22.22%). [17] Vincente et al.,2019 studied the clinical and histopathological characteristics of the cohort of 125 patients with OSCC which was composed of 82 men and 43 women, ranging from 28 to 91 years, with a median age of 57 years. [18] In the present study out of 211 cases, 178(84.3%) were males and only 33(15.6%) were females with M:F being 5:1. Our study aligns with the research conducted by Lin et al. in 2015, which involved 305 patients with OSCC, of which 236 (77.3%) were males and 69 (22.6%) were females. Similarly, Yoshida et al. conducted a study in 2018 on 135 patients with OSCC, where 80 (59.2%) were males and 55 (40.7%) were females. [15,17]

In our study, the tongue was identified as the most common site of Oral Squamous Cell Carcinoma (OSCC). Out of total 211 cases, 92 (43.6%) were located on the tongue followed by the 79(37.4%) cases on the buccal mucosa. In our study, histopathological grade wise of 211 cases of OSCC, 107(51.6%) cases were of well differentiated OSCC, 87(42.1%) cases were of moderately differentiated and 17(8%) cases were of poorly differentiated OSCC. Troeltzsch et al.,2017 conducted a study on 88 patients of OSCC out of which 58(65.9%) cases were of moderately differentiated OSCC, 16(18.2%) of well differentiated OSCC and 14(15.9%) cases were of poorly differentiated OSCC. [20]

In our study out of 65 cases of OSCC positive immunohistochemical staining for PD-L1 in tumour cells was 50.8%. Out of 21 premalignant squamous lesions, PD-L1 expression was observed in 62%. The correlation of PD-L1 positivity with the number/proportion of OSCC and premalignant lesions was found to be insignificant

($p > 0.05$). Among the 21 premalignant lesions, 13(62%) cases showed positive immuno-expression for PD-L1 whereas 8(38%) cases were negative. The p-value of PD-L1 positive versus negative cases was found to be 0.373 which was statistically insignificant ($p > 0.05$). Therefore, the correlation of histopathologically diagnosed cases of OSCC and premalignant lesions with PD-L1 immuno-expression was found to be insignificant.

Troeltzsch et al., 2017 conducted a study on 88 patients of OSCC and found that a considerable proportion of OSCCs (29/88 OSCC specimens; 29%) exhibit clinically significant PD-L1 expression.[20] In a study conducted by Maruse et al.,2018 the expression of PD-L1 was determined immunohistochemically in 97 patients of OSCC and the association of this expression with clinicopathological characteristics was examined, Increased expression of PD-L1 was found in 64.9% of OSCC cases. [11] Kouketsu et al.,2019 examined 106 OSCC and 79 OEPL specimens for PD-L1 expression by immunohistochemistry. [14] In OSCC and OEPL specimens, PD-L1 expression was detected predominantly in epithelial or carcinoma cells. Seventy-two OSCC (67.9%) and 21 OEPL (26.6%) specimens were positive for PD-L1. PD-L1 expression levels were significantly different between OEPL and OSCC specimens ($p < 0.001$). There were significant positive correlations between PD-L1 expression in OEPL and OSCC specimens ($p < 0.001$) and these findings were discordant with our study. [14]

In the present study of the 65 cases, 50.7% OSCC cases showed positive immuno-expression and 49.2% cases showed no immuno-expression for PD-L1 in tumour cells. When compared grade wise, poorly differentiated OSCC showed PD-L1 immuno-expression in maximum number of cases comprising of 88.2% (15/17) cases as opposed to well differentiated OSCC which showed PD-L1 immuno-expression only in 27.5%(8/29) cases. The observed difference in PD-L1 positive versus negative staining score among different grades was statistically significant ($p < 0.05$). Cho et al.,2011 in their study found that out of 45 cases of OSCC,

moderately differentiated tumours had strong PD-L1 expression compared with well-differentiated OSCC, but no significant association of PD-L1 expression with histological grade was observed, which is not in agreement with our observation. [21] Kouketsu et al., 2019 found that even though PD-L1 immuno-expression in the 106 OSCC specimens did not significantly correlate with the degree of differentiation (p value=0.0742), high PD-L1 and expression was frequently observed in OSCC specimens with poor differentiation. [14] In contrast to our findings, Vicente et al. conducted a study in 2019 on 125 specimens of OSCC. They found no significant relationship between PD-L1 expression and the tumor grade and stage. [18]

In the present study as per the degree of stromal lymphocyte reaction, 11(61.6%) cases having absent/mild TILs exhibited PDL-1 score 3 whereas 27(75%) cases having marked TILs showed PD-L1 score 0. The p value of PD-L1 was found to be <0.001. In a study involving 45 cases of oral squamous cell carcinoma (OSCC) by Cho et al., 2011 they conducted immunohistochemical examinations to assess PD-L1 expression and the degree of lymphocyte infiltration. They observed PD-L1 expression on OSCC cells in 39 cases, and this was notably associated with a lower density of intratumoral CD8(+) TILs, with a p-value of 0.047. These findings align with the results obtained in our study. [21] Mattox et al., 2017 examined 53 OSCCs, of which 79% (42/53) were found to express PD-L1 and this expression of PD-L1 was associated with moderate to high levels of CD4+ and CD8+ TIL. [22] Maruse et al., 2018 found in their study on 97 patients that there was no significant correlation between PD-L1 immuno-expression and stromal lymphoplasmacytic infiltration which is not in agreement with our study. [11] whereas in a study conducted by Kouketsu et al., 2019 they found that there was significant correlations between PD-L1 (concordant with our study) in OSCC specimens and stromal lymphocytic reaction (p < 0.05). [14]

In our study, T3 tumour size OSCC showed PD-L1 immuno-expression in majority of cases comprising of 84.6% (11/13) as opposed to T2 stage OSCC which was positive only in 52.3% (11/21) cases. The difference in PD-L1 staining among different TNM stage groups was statistically significant (p value=0.00034). This indicates that as the tumor size increases and the TNM stage progresses from T2 to T3, there is a concurrent increase in the immunoexpression of PD-L1. Maruse et al., 2018 in their study on 97 patients found that there was no significant correlation observed between PD-L1 immuno-expression and tumour size which is discordant with our study. [11] However, in 2019, Kouketsu et al. investigated 106 OSCC specimens for PD-L1 expression and,

consistent with our findings, reported a significant correlation between PD-L1 immunoreactivity and tumor size (p < 0.05). Also PD-L1 immunoreactivity in cases with advanced TNM staging was significantly higher than that in low staging cases (P < 0.01). [14] Naruse et al., 2020 examined PD-L1 immuno-expression among 121 patients with OSCC and found that 57.9% were positive for PD-L1 immunohistochemically. There was no significant statistical correlation found between PD-L1 (p value=0.759) which is in discordant with our study. [23]

In our investigation, a statistically significant correlation was identified between cervical lymph node status and PD-L1 staining, with a positive cervical lymph node status showing statistical significance (p < 0.05).

In the present study, of the total 65 cases, metastasis was present only in 2(4.4%) cases. The association of positive PD-L1 staining with distant metastasis was statistically insignificant (p>0.05). Similar to our study Lin et al., 2015 analyzed PD-L1 immuno-expression by immunohistochemistry in 305 cancer specimens from primary OSCC patients in which they found that the patients with distant metastasis also had high PD-L1 expression (p=0.0103). [15] However Kouketsu et al., 2019 in their study found that the PD-L1 immuno-expression in the 106 OSCC specimens did not significantly correlate with metastasis, recurrence, postoperative metastasis, or survival which is in agreement with our study. [14] Chen et al., 2019 conducted a study on 41 OSCC specimens and found that PD-L1 immuno-expression was detected in 97.6% of OSCC. [24] But there was no significant statistical correlation found between this expression and distant metastasis. (p value=0.2774), a finding concordant with our study.

In our study, stage 4 OSCC showed PD-L1 immuno-expression in all the cases accounting for 100% (07/07) cases as opposed to stage 2 OSCC which showed PD-L1 immuno-expression only in 36.3% (04/11). The p value of PD-L1 was found to be 0.00015. Statistically the difference in PDL-1 staining among different TNM stage groups was found to be highly significant (p<0.01) Similar to the findings in our study, Kouketsu et al., 2019 in their study on 106 OSCC cases found that the PD-L1 immuno-expression in the cases with advanced TNM staging was significantly higher than that in cases with low staging (p < 0.01). [14] However Vicente et al., 2019 conducted a study on 125 specimens of OSCC in which they found that there was no any significant relationship between PD-L1 expression and the tumour grade and stage which is not in agreement with our study. [18] Khan et al., 2020 conducted a study on 140 participants in which PD-L1 immuno-expression was observed in

62.1% cases. [13] A statistically significant p-value was found between the association of PD-L1 with stage II and IV tumours. (p-values: 0.029, 0.001) which is a finding similar with the findings in our study. [25] Mishra et al., 2021 performed PD-L1 IHC in 93 OSCC cases and found that no statistically significant correlation noted between PD-L1 score and tumour grade or stage which is discordant with our study. [20]

In our study, of the 65 patients of OSCC, 36 patients could be followed up for a period of 1 year. As per the observation the association of positive PD-L1 staining with tumour recurrence was statistically insignificant ($p > 0.05$). Of the total 36 patients that were followed up and alive, OSCC cases showed PD-L1 immuno-expression 55.5% (20/36). Kogashiwa et al., 2017 in a study demonstrated that PD-L1 was expressed in 52.4% of locally advanced OSCC cases and found that PD-L1 positivity was significantly associated with overall ($p = 0.008$) survival of the patients which is a finding discordant with our study. [26] Maruse et al., 2018 revealed that patients with PD-L1 expression had a significantly poorer prognosis than those without PD-L1 expression. [11] Yoshida et al., 2018 observed a positive correlation with lymph node metastasis but no positive correlation was demonstrated between PD-L1 expression and overall survival which is in agreement with our study. [17] Kouketsu et al., 2019 found that PD-L1 immunoreactivity in the 106 OSCC specimens did not significantly correlate with recurrence, postoperative metastasis, or survival which is concordant with our study. [14] Naruse et al., 2020 examined PD-L1 immuno-expression among 121 patients with OSCC and found the expression of PD-L1 was significantly associated with local recurrence in patients with OSCC ($p < 0.01$ and $p < 0.01$, respectively) which is not in agreement with our study. [23] They also demonstrated a significant decrease in 5-year disease specific survival rate for patients with combined PD-L1+/PD-L1+ expressions ($p < 0.05$). [23]

In our study a significant correlation was found between the immuno-expression of PD-L1 and tumour grade (p value=0.00036), stromal lymphocyte reaction (p value<0.0001), tumour size (p value=0.00034), cervical lymph node status (p value<0.0001), and tumour stage (p value=0.00015). Higher tumour grade was significantly associated with higher expression of PD-L1 and significantly higher PD-L1 was correlated with higher tumour stage. Various studies like Kogashiwa et al., 2017, Maruse et al., 2018 and Naruse et al., 2020 have also revealed that locally advanced tumours have higher PD-L1 expression (similar to our observations) and patients with higher PD-L1 expression had a

significantly poorer prognosis than those without PD-L1 expression. [11,23,26].

Bauml et al., 2017 in their study demonstrated that 17% of patients with PD-L1 expression of >1% of tumour cells responded to treatment with nivolumab thus improving prognosis. [27] Based on current established treatment protocols and clinical trials PD-L1 immuno-expression in tumour cells can help in the prediction of the prognosis of these patients and also can help to predict the response to the treatment given specially with the PD-L1 monoclonal antibodies.

Conclusion

The present study was a two year prospective study which evaluated the histopathological spectrum of 211 study cases of oral squamous cell carcinomas (OSCC) and 41 premalignant lesions received in the Department of Pathology over a period of two years from November 2019 to November 2021. A total of 325 oral biopsies were received out of which 223 (68.6%) were of oral squamous cell carcinoma (OSCC), 41 (12.6%) cases of oral squamous premalignant lesions and 61 (18.7%) cases of non-squamous malignancies, granulomatous and non-specific inflammatory lesions.

The main aim of the present study was to know whether relevant PD-L1 expression can be detected in OSCC and premalignant squamous lesions and their correlation with various clinicopathological variables which might show the importance of the interplay of PD-L1 pathway in this tumour. Immunohistochemical analysis of PD-L1 was done in 86 representative biopsies (65 OSCC and 21 premalignant) and the correlation of immuno-expression of PD-L1 in tumour cells was assessed with regard to clinicopathological variables such as histopathological grade, intensity score, degree of stromal lymphocyte reaction/Tumour infiltrating lymphocytes (TILs), tumour size, nodal status and tumour stage specially. In our study a significant statistical correlation was found between the immuno-expression of PD-L1 in tumour cells and tumour grade (p value=0.0003), degree of stromal lymphocyte reaction (p value<0.0001), tumour size (p value=0.0003), cervical lymph node status (p value<0.0001) and tumour stage (p value=0.0001). Higher tumour grade and higher TNM stage were significantly associated with higher expression of PD-L1. PD-L1 immuno-expression was not found to have any significant association with recurrence and could not predict the overall survival owing to limited period of study and lesser number of patients in follow-up. Thus the observed significant correlation of PD-L1 with different clinicopathological variables especially tumor grade and TNM stage can help in the prediction of the

prognosis of these patients and can also help guide the response to the treatment given in higher stage tumour, specially with the promising PD-L1 monoclonal antibodies.

Strengths and future scope of this study:

The FDA approval of the monoclonal antibodies such as pembrolizumab and nivolumab for the treatment of Head and Neck squamous cell cancer has sparked a new hope in patient population that has a 50% recurrence rate and poor survival rate despite aggressive multi-modality treatment involving surgery, radiotherapy, chemotherapy. It is becoming increasingly important and rewarding for onco-pathologists to assess this immuno-expression to potentially improve patient survival rates. Our study analyzed this immuno-expression of PD-L1 in OSCC and its association, particularly with prognostic factors like tumor grade and stage. In our study, a higher tumor grade was significantly associated with higher expression of PD-L1, and a significantly higher PD-L1 was correlated with a higher tumor stage. Based on established treatment protocols and clinical trials, this can aid in predicting the prognosis of these patients and can also help predict the response to the given treatment, especially the promising PD-L1 monoclonal antibodies. This could potentially lead to more personalized and effective treatment strategies for patients with OSCC.

Limitation of our study:

Small sample size of the study may not be representative of the whole population. Due to the time constraints of the study design, it was not possible to conduct a complete 2-year and 5-year follow-up of the patients. Therefore, this data does not reflect the evaluation of the overall 5-year recurrence, survival, and prognosis. The antibody clones used for PD-L1 assessment can vary significantly across different studies. This variation could potentially influence the positive and negative immuno-expression of OSCC cases as a whole. The scoring system for PD-L1 and the threshold for its percentage expression have been subjects of debate, given that various researchers have employed different values in their studies. This can be attributed to the variation in the overall results. Many studies in which Anti PD-L1 monoclonal antibodies are given as a therapy to assess the cure rate are still in their various phases of clinical trials. So as of now it is difficult to predict the future treatment outcome and long-term improvement in the prognosis of the patients. As a result, the significance of PD-L1 as predictive and prognostic biomarker in OSCC patients can be assessed by further research works with larger sample size and patients

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